

Warok's Success to Keep Power with the Tradition of Javanic Political Thinking

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Abstract

This research will discuss about the succession of Warok to maintain power in the tradition of Javanese political thought. Warok are local strongmen trying to maintain power in the midst of Javanese society where the capital/strength they have is only physical strength or also called "*kasekten*" and wisdom. This study uses qualitative methods coupled with analysis of documents, decisions, speeches, bibliographies, and press reports about actions / events. This research itself will also use the method of interview, observation, and documentation where the interview will be conducted with Warok as the main informant in this study. The conclusion of this research is Warok with physical strength and wisdom in the end can always maintain his power. It is different from politics in other places which get power by means of violence, doctrine, or giving money. In Java, it turns out to have a tendency to two things, namely one's identity and also "*sakti*" which reflects one's level of divinity.

Keywords: *Local Strongmen, Javanese Politics, Warok, Local Politics.*

INTRODUCTION

This research will discuss about the succession of Warok to maintain power in the tradition of Javanese political thought. Warok are local strongmen trying to maintain power in the midst of Javanese society where the capital/strength they have is only physical strength or also called "*kasekten*" and wisdom.

Indonesia has a history of organized territorial crime groups controlled by local strongmen who act as '*brokers*' with non-criminal members of society (Bakker, 2017, pp. 134-135). Before the arrival of the Dutch, society in Indonesia was characterized by the emergence of bandits, fighters, mercenaries, mystics, warlords, kings, and other groups that used violence. These groups seek to provide social control and control over natural resources either through negotiation, alliance formation, in addition to the use of rituals or the manifestation of violence. This situation then gave rise to the seeds of *local Strongmen* who were later dubbed '*jago*' (Wilson, 2015, p. 11). In addition, the rules in the colonial era that ultimately formed the '*king*' or '*sultan*' at the local level as well as the aristocracy at the regional level represented the concentration of power and authority in the archipelago (Mysbergh, 1957). These '*kings*' and '*sultans*' eventually became rulers at the local level and also became part of the government to maintain its power.

The third wave of democratization prompted the rise of elite research because of the suitability of elite theory for the study of rapid political transformation. Along with this revival, many new theoretical understandings of elite behavior have emerged as well as empirical research on the follow-up to regime change (Lopez, 2013, p. 9). The history of pre-democratic politics in Southeast Asian countries where thugs have become a feature of modern democratic life which is a legacy of colonialism. This also happened in Indonesia where in the pre-independence period, colonial power and central and regional power relations emerged and then the thugs emerged in the era of the struggle for independence and subsequently took their position in post-independence politics (Wilson, 2015, p. 11).

Migdal further explained, this phenomenon emerged based on three interrelated arguments. *First*, local strongmen thrive in a society that is similar to a network. Thanks to this network-like structure, local strongmen gained significant influence beyond that of formal local leaders and bureaucrats. *Second*, local strongmen exercise social control by utilizing an important component that the community believes to be a '*survival strategy*'. The survival logic provides an opportunity for local strongmen not only to build their legitimacy in the eyes of the people who expect compassion to fulfill their basic needs, but also to expand their power. *Third*, local strongmen directly or indirectly have succeeded in limiting the capacity of state institutions and apparatus, causing the government to become weak (Agustino & Yusoff, 2010, p. 13).

The historical sequence will help Javanese political researchers to determine the origin of the current power of the local strongmen. The linkage of past history, especially culture and people's beliefs, becomes a benchmark for the influence of local strongmen to come to power in the present. Warok, which is a part of the past, in fact still has a strong influence in society and can even influence formal institutions such as the government. Therefore, this study will discuss how Warok maintained his power in the tradition of Javanese political thought. Furthermore, the question that will be answered is how the Warok who were part of the past could maintain power in Java? How are beliefs and culture used as Warok's tools to maintain power in the present?.

METHODS

This study uses qualitative as a method where the use of qualitative methods by Historical Institutionalism (HI) aims to identify several events that have the potential for the desired outcome. Mahoney, Kimball, and Koivu (2009) asked how one determines which of two or more critical junctures is a potential source of a desired outcome. The choice of focus has methodological implications, Historical Institutionalism (HI) researchers continue by analyzing documents, decisions, speeches, bibliographies, and press reports on actions/events. (Sanders, 2006, p. 44) This research itself will also use the method of interview, observation, and documentation where the interview will be conducted with Warok as the main informant in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Historical Institutionalism as Perspective

The *historical institutionalism (HI)* perspective focuses on what Sorensen (2015, 18) calls "the creation, persistence, and change of institutions over time" and Sanders (2006, p. 42) calls it "construction, maintenance, and adaptation" of institutions." From this perspective, there are two key concepts, namely *path dependence* and *critical juncture* (Karim, 2018, p. 17). HI is always dependent on *path dependence* (PD) so it is used as the key to understanding distal causation. Many institutional settings depend on *path dependence* (PD) giving rise to endogenous mechanisms of reproduction and positive feedback that sustains them, limits or limits change (Capoccia, 2016, p. 13).

In addition, the *Historical Institutionalism (HI)* perspective strongly supports the image of social causation which is referred to as *path dependence* (PD) in the sense that it supports the view that the effect of power will be mediated by contextual features of a particular situation that are often inherited from the past (Hall & Taylor, 1996, p. 941). Unlike other types of historical causes, Collier and Collier state that *critical junctures* (CJ) produce inheritances that can reproduce themselves without the persistent presence or recurrence of the originating cause. Simplified, *critical junctures* mark the beginning of a *path-dependent* process (Fioretos, Falleti, & Sheingate, 2016, p. 9). CJ are times when substantial institutional changes occur that create 'branching points' of historical development moving on new paths (Hall & Taylor, 1996, p. 942).

Path dependence (PD) refers to continuity within the institution. In the view of *historical institutionalists*, institutions are conservative and tend to persist in a form that has been achieved at a certain point in time. The durability of a form of institutional relationship occurs when there is *positive feedback* from individuals so that they continue it from time to time. Other forms of institutional relations may emerge, but without *positive feedback* these forms will not survive. Institutions, in the end, are the result of the contestation of a number of forms of relations through several historical moments and conflicts. The more complex a society, the more complex the contestation in that society (Karim, 2018).

The explicit relationship of CJ's approach to PD provides a powerful theoretical tool for historical causal analysis. The emphasis placed in PD theory on mechanisms of institutional reproduction, dynamics of increasing returns, and network effects provides strong theoretical support for the thesis that decisions and developments that lie in the past can have long-term effects on future institutional arrangements. In Political Science to explicitly theorize that as long as CJ has various development possibilities that will occur, and the previous structural conditions do not necessarily determine the type and direction of subsequent institutional development (Goldstone 1998; Mahoney 2000; Capoccia, 2016, p. 2).

Collier and Collier argue that variations in *critical juncture* exposure across multiple contexts hold the key to explaining political heritage and yielding differing results across countries. They emphasize the importance of determining the duration of the critical juncture as well as the impact of historical heritage and highlight that the timing of the critical juncture is closely related to other developments (Fioretos, Falleti, & Sheingate, 2016, p. 9).

If viewed from the time span, then CJ will have a shorter time when compared to *path-dependent*. In addition, if the CJ period is considered a long period, then the substantial influence of institutions is limited by institutional constraints that will reappear. Therefore, Capoccia and Kelemen suggest focusing on turning points to provide a more complete understanding of how and when political actors stop reproductive mechanisms and create new institutions or modify existing ones (Fioretos, Falleti, & Sheingate, 2016, p. 9). The concept of CJ in *path-dependent institutions* analysis refers to a situation of uncertainty in which actor decisions are very important in determining the choice of an institutional development path over other possible paths (Capoccia, 2016, p. 1).

Kelle S. Tsai's writings on historical institutionalism (IR) are very interesting to observe to describe the transformation in IR. According to Tsai, IR has traditionally focused on formal institutions designed and enforced by official entities in advanced industrial democracies. However, the modalities of endogenous institutional change described by IR reveal that the causal mechanisms of institutional transformation are usually informal. Tsai proposes a more inclusive ontology of institutions that views institutions as two-dimensional Möbius pathways with formal and informal components regardless of regime type or level of economic development. Focusing on the emerging "adaptive informal institutions" in a multi-tiered institutional

context can demonstrate how informal institutions compromise, subvert, and even facilitate reform of formal institutions (Tsai, 2016, p. 1).

The tendency to prioritize formal institutions reflects in part the fact that historical institutionalism grew out of the study of advanced industrial democracies. In contrast, attempts to take informal institutions seriously stem mainly from research in developing countries and transition economies where some types of formal institutions may be less institutionalized than informal ones (Tsai, 2016, p. 2).

It is therefore necessary to trace the origin and reproduction of informal institutions, which, in turn, provide a basis for identifying the sources of change in informal institutions. Applying these recommendations is not intuitive for historical institutionalism, given its traditional emphasis on official rule and public policy. However, as suggested earlier, the modalities of endogenous institutional change described by historical institutionalists represent an actually informal process. Analytically, the next logical step is to theorize processes such as informal institutions are adaptive as they repeat themselves in patterns (Tsai, 2016, p. 11).

Therefore, future research should start from Möbius' stripe premise that all institutional system ecosystems include both formal and informal components, regardless of regime type, level of development, or geographic area. Such an attitude will encourage students to interrogate the origin, reproduction, and evolution of informal institutions in interaction with the dynamics derived from the study of formal institutions in historical institutions (Tsai, 2016, p. 16).

The Emergence of Warok

The first appearance of Warok was in the era of Raden Batahara Katong who was the first Regent of Ponorogo. If seen in Serat Centhini, Majapahit is described as a great kingdom under the reign of Brawijaya V which in its Volume III, mentions about 101 names that are considered descendants of Brawijaya, such as Bathara Katong which is the nickname of Jaka Pitutur alias Raden Arakkali who served as Duke of Ponorogo (Putranto, 2003).

Until now, Batoro Katong is considered the most legendary figure and first ruler in the Ponorogo community. Batoro Katong is a symbol of political power that has been preserved by the authorities in this area from time to time. No ruler of Ponorogo can escape this legendary historical figure (Sari & Sasmito, 2020, p. 28).

In this context, the existence of Islam as a teaching is then mixed with power that intersects with politics. The expansion of Islam has a direct impact on the expansion of influence, and it also means that power and Batoro Katong are idealized figures, rulers and scholars (Sari & Sasmito, 2020, p. 23).

The appearance of the first warok, namely Warok Suromenggolo, marked the emergence of the influence and spread of power possessed by Warok. The spread of Islam in Java had an influence on social and political developments at that time and after, and one of the influential figures in socio-political developments, especially in the Ponorogo area, was Warok Suromenggolo. He is a warok figure who has a great influence on the community, as evidenced by his name that always appears in dance demonstrations, which shows that people always remember the presence of Warok Suromenggolo, who is friendly, friendly, humble, and loved by his people (Sari & Sasmito, 2020, p. 5).

Warok Suromenggolo although known as a Hindu figure, but he was close and open to the arrival of Islam, never even rejected the presence of Islam in his society, giving up reog as a means of introducing Islamic culture into Hindu culture at that time. It is not an exaggeration if the figure of Warok Suromenggolo is one of the actors behind the success of the presence of the Islamic community which reaches 99% in Ponorogo today (jatim.kemenag.go.id, 2014; Sari & Sasmito, 2020, p. 5).

Suromenggolo is a warok figure who is close to the community, his attitude of life is always devoted as a loyal retainer, presenting the trust given to him in return with a loyal attitude and he maintains that loyalty. He was relieved when his father Ki Ageng Kutu was attacked by Bathoro Katong, even remained cooperative. This made Raden Bathoro Katong not hesitate to take him as a personal bodyguard after the death of his father Ki Ageng Kutu (Sari & Sasmito, 2020, p. 5).

His cooperative attitude was always shown when Bathoro Katong and Ki Ageng Mirah were tasked with spreading the religion of Islam by running as loyal retainers. He had a high tolerance for other religions (Islam) even though at that time he was Hindu. Although he is full of mystique as a warok, he is known as someone who is straight, firm in his opinion and is not tempted by position. His whole life was dedicated to being Bathoro Katong's personal bodyguard even though he was given the position of Demang Kartosari (Prmono, 2006; Sari & Sasmito, 2020, p. 5).

According to Khoirurrosyidin (2014), with the participation of Suromenggolo in Bathoro Katong's government, the role of warok in the world of politics appears, in this case Suromenggolo's role in launching Bathoro Katong's government. Thus, the role of warok has two functions, namely as a figure in the arts and culture, as well as being involved in the world of politics. Because the role of warok was given by Bathoro Katong as his personal bodyguard, the people felt the role of warok as a stabilizer by affiliated with the ruler and following who was in power (Sari & Sasmito, 2020, p. 48).

Warok Succession in Javanese Political Thought Tradition

Warok's triumph in achieving success in the royal era was also supported by the Javanese tradition of political thought where the Javanese political thought tradition usually emphasized signs of concentration of power, not demonstrations of its implementation or use. These signs are seen both in the holder of power and in the society in which he exercises his power. The two, of course, are closely related. One of Indonesia's most prominent contemporary intellectuals said, "The central concept in the traditional Javanese way of life is the direct relationship between a person's inner state and his ability to control his environment" (Anderson, 1972, p. 13).

The most obvious sign of a person in power is, consistently enough, his ability to concentrate: to focus his own personal strength, to absorb forces from without, and to concentrate within himself that seems contradictory. The first type of concentration we have discussed briefly, suffice it to say here that the image of asceticism is the main expression of concentrated Power. The ability to absorb the concentration of external forces is a frequent theme in both wayang legends and historical traditions. One characteristic feature, which relates this type of absorption to the opponent's concentration, is the battle between the hero and a strong foe, in which the enemy who is defeated in death enters the hero's body, increasing the power of his conqueror. A famous example in wayang literature is the story of King Parta entering Arjuna's body after losing a battle. But other stories, such as those depicting the spirit of Begawan Bagaspati descending on Judistira to allow him to kill King Salya, or the fusion of Srikandi and Ambalika to cover the destruction of Rishi Bhishma at the start of the Brajuda War, reveal a parallel pattern in which Power is absorbed from external sources (Anderson, 1972, p. 13).

But no less striking and from a historical perspective perhaps of more enduring significance is the ability to center opposites. This classic iconographic symbol is a combination of male and female. In ancient Javanese art, this combination does not take the form of a hermaphrodite from the Hellenistic world, an ambiguous transitional being between the sexes, but rather a form of being in which masculine and feminine characteristics are sharply juxtaposed (Anderson, 1972, p. 14). The social signs of concentration of Power are fertility, prosperity, stability, and nobility. As said by the puppeteer of wayang beber in the classic description of the ancient Javanese kingdom of Kediri (Anderson, 1972, p. 18).

The two fundamental ideas behind this conventional image are creativity (fertility-prosperity) and harmony (*tranquility-order*), expressed in the ancient motto that is so often on the lips of contemporary elites, *tata tentrem karta rahardja* (order, peace, prosperity, good fortune). Both fertility and order are merely expressions of Power. Strength is the ability to give life. Power is also the ability to maintain a smooth firmness and act like a magnet aligning iron filings scattered in a patterned force field. On the other hand, the signs of the diminishing firmness of the ruler's power and the diffusion of his power are seen equally in the manifestations of chaos in nature—floods, eruptions, and plagues—and in the modes of inappropriate social behavior—thrift, greed, and murder (Anderson, 1972).

Again, it must be remembered that in Javanese thought there is no reciprocal effect between the decline of power and the emergence of this undesirable phenomenon. Antisocial behavior arises from the declining power of the ruler but does not in itself reduce that power. This is a symptom but not the cause of the decrease. Therefore, a ruler who once allowed natural and social chaos to arise finds it very difficult to reorganize his authority. The Javanese tend to believe that, if he still had Power, chaos would never arise. They ultimately do not stem from autonomous social or economic conditions, but from leeway or the diffusion of power within the state (Anderson, 1972, p. 19).

The Glory of Warok Kingdom Period

Since the beginning of the formation of Ponorogo, the community has established *warok* as a symbol of a leader. The characteristics possessed such as rich in knowledge and magic, helping spirit, protecting family and society, being fair and honest, made *warok* as the ideal figure desired. *Warok* is a figure who has advantages in terms of the science of *kanuragan* (immunity) and has a spiritual soul that places him in a high position in the Ponorogo society. In the art of *reog* this figure is described as an army that relies on the truth in the battle between good and bad (Krismawati, Wartyo, & Suryani, 2018, p. 117).

Warok is a central figure who has great influence in both the lower classes and the political elite. During the time of Bathara Katong, *warok* played the role of a demang or village leader who had political influence. His position as a leader and person in charge in the art of *reog*, as well as the decision regarding the addition of the *warok* dance component in the art, made him a cultural figure who further strengthened his position in society. In its development, *warok* became a strategic elite who had a strong influence so that it was taken into account by the ruling elite. This is supported by the reality that *warok* are local elites, most of whom are members of the regional executive and legislature. When viewed in terms of status or honor, the *warok* is in the upper class in the social strata of the Ponorogo community (Krismawati, Wartyo, & Suryani, 2018, p. 117).

According to Warok Djarot, in ancient times what was called *warok* Ponorogo, yes people who at that time had advantages which in the sense of being given advantages by Allah SWT so that they were given advantages, especially this was in

their '*parogo*' (body). They are usually people who were called warok in ancient times who were in power, so that what was their request was blessed by Allah SWT (*Interview with Warok Djarot*).

There are three virtues that a *warok* must possess, namely, *Sucining swara* (purity of voice), *Sucining roso* (purity of taste), and *Sucining tenogo* (purity of energy). Virtue can be possessed by believing and praising the one who speaks with mantras and prayers, worshiping those who create motion and perform prayers and meditation. The religion adhered to and the Javanese culture that is still firmly held in the end has an impact on the ritual behavior carried out by the *warok* group. It can be seen that the *warok* have believed in Allah and carried out his orders by performing prayers and doing meditation as a form of Javanese spiritual *play*. Based on this explanation, it can be concluded that after the collapse of the Wengker Kingdom, the majority of *waroks* were Muslim but still held *plays* from Hindu teachings such as imprisoned or referred to as the *abangan* group. In addition, a series of fasting which is also prioritized in Islam is also carried out as a form of effort to restrain lust (Krismawati, Wartyo, & Suryani, 2018, p. 119).

Warok ritual behavior is based on the outward aspect which is seen as a reflection of the subtle and inner essential reality. The relationship between the two, both hierarchically and coordinated, must go hand in hand and maintain harmony. A harmony can be achieved if humans are able to cleanse their minds, protect themselves from the harsh world, live a moral life that is in accordance with the social order, and train their senses so that they are beneficial to themselves and not harmful to others. Meanwhile, *warok's* efforts to achieve inner peace and true knowledge are carried out by avoiding material and gross things and increasing their subtle abilities so that they can achieve enlightenment and moral existence. This proves that the *warok's* thinking is still in line with the Javanese style of thought and culture in general (Krismawati, Wartyo, & Suryani, 2018, p. 123).

In addition to performing rituals and *tirakat*, the *warok* group is required to have nine virtues consisting of, clean and pure heart, not committing a crime, being honest, sincere, and careful in carrying out all activities, reducing lustful desires, always remembering the essence of a life by seeking inner perfection, and good at adapting, not discriminating, compassionate to others, honest and spiritual, and living obediently to God. This should be a consideration in converting someone into a true *warok*. However, in its development, many people call themselves *warok* on the basis of their wealth, strength, and supernatural knowledge. Therefore, it is not uncommon for this group to carry out *molimo* which is even strictly prohibited in the principle of living life as *warok*. Meanwhile, *spitting* behavior which is said to be a form of kanuragan ideology, belongs to the traditional actions carried out on the basis of the prevailing habits in society (Krismawati, Wartyo, & Suryani, 2018, pp. 123-124).

CONCLUSION

Based on the above discussion, it can be concluded that Warok could maintain power in Java by using a more holistic culture or tradition of Javanese political thought. Javanese politics is different where holistic is still the thing that most determines someone in power. The animist belief in dynamism that is strongly embedded in the culture and traditions of the people also influences political developments in Java. Maintaining power means preserving the sources or means of gaining power, where what Warok is currently doing is preserving Javanese cultural traditions. Maintaining Javanese cultural traditions can be interpreted as Warok guarding his instrument of power in the form of the *kejawen* tradition (Javanese tradition) which considers strong and sacred people to occupy the highest position in society. The preservation of this tradition ultimately gave power to Warok from the royal era until now. Even now, the existence of the Waroks is still considered, either at the time of general elections or at cultural events held by the community. As long as this *kejawen* culture or tradition is still strong and attached to the community, it means that it is certain that the power of Warok will also continue to exist. But that culture will clash with the development of the era where a new generation will appear and no longer know the *kejawen* culture or tradition. It will be interesting to study in the future how modernization or the development of information technology will affect the power of Warok itself.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Agustino, L., & Yusoff, M. A. (2010). Politik lokal di Indonesia: dari otokratik ke reformasi politik. *Jurnal Ilmu Politik*.
- [2]. Anderson, B. (1972). *The Idea of Power In Javanese Culture*. Cornell University Press.
- [3]. Aspinall, E. (2011). Democratization and Ethic Politics in Indonesia: Nine Theses. *Journal of East Asian Studies*.
- [4]. Bakker, L. (2017). Chapter Title: Militias, Security and Citizenship in Indonesia. Dalam H. S. Ward Berenschot, *Book Title: Citizenship and Democratization in Southeast Asia*. Brill.
- [5]. Capoccia, G. (2016). Critical Juntures. Dalam O. Fioretos, T. G. Falleti, & A. Sheingate, *The Oxford Handbook of Historical Institutionalism* (hal. 843). United Kingdom: Oxford University press.
- [6]. Efferin, S. Darmadji, & Y., T. (2004). *Metode Penelitian Untuk Akuntansi : Sebuah Pendekatan Praktis*. Malang: Bayumedia Publishing.

- [7]. Fioretos, O., Falleti, T. G., & Sheingate, A. (2016). Historical Institutionalism in Political Science. Dalam O. Fioretos, T. G. Falleti, & A. Sheingate, *The Oxford Handbook of Historical Institutionalism* (hal. 843). United Kingdom: Oxford University Press.
- [8]. Hall, P. A., & Taylor, R. C. (1996). Political Science and the Three New Institutionalisms. *Political Studies*.
- [9]. Haryanto. (2009). Elit Poltiik Lokal dalam Perubahan Sistem Politik. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik*.
- [10]. Haryanto. (2017). *Elit, Massa, dan Kekuasaan: Suatu Bahasan Pengantar*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit PolGov.
- [11]. Karim, R. A. (2018). *MENEGOSIASI ULANG INDONESIA Perubahan Politik dan Peran Lembaga-lembaga Agama di Manado dan Sumenep dalam Era Awal Reformasi (1999-2005)*. Yogyakarta: Program Studi S3 Dept. Politik dan Pemerintahan Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik Universitas Gadjah Mada Yogyakarta.
- [12]. Khoirurrosyidin. (2014). Dinamika Peran Warok dalam Politik di Ponorogo. *Jurnal Humanity*.
- [13]. Koentjaraningrat. (1984). *Kebudayaan Jawa*. Jakarta: Balai Pustaka.
- [14]. Krismawati, N. U., Wartyo, & Suryani, N. (2018). Eksistensi Warok Dan Gemblak di tengah Masyarakat Muslim Ponorogo Tahun 1960-1980. *Religió: Jurnal Studi Agama-agama*.
- [15]. Lopez, M. (2013). Elite Theory. *Sociopedia.isa*.
- [16]. Masaaki, O., & Hamid, A. (2008). Jawa in Power, 1999—2007. *Southeast Asia Program Publications*.
- [17]. Mysbergh, J. H. (1957). The Indonesian Elite. *Far Eastern Survey*.
- [18]. Rofiq, A. C. (2020). *HISTORIOGRAFI LOKAL Babad Ponorogo Dan Kepahlawanan Masyarakat Ponorogo*. Yogyakarta: Bintang Pustaka Madani.
- [19]. Rozaki, A. (2009). Social origin dan Politik Kuasa Blater di Madura. *Kyoto Review of Southeast Asia Issue 11*.
- [20]. Sanders, E. (2006). Historical Institutionalism. Dalam R. E. Goodin, *The Oxford Handbook of Political Science* (hal. 835). New York: Oxford University Press.
- [21]. Suhaedi, H. (2006). Kekuasaan, Kekerasan dan Mobilitas Jawa. *AL QALAM*.
- [22]. Taufiq, A. (2013). Perilaku Ritual Warok Ponorogo Dalam Perspektif Teori Tindakan Max Weber. *Jurnal Sosiologi Islam*.
- [23]. Tilly, C. (2006). Why And How History Matters. Dalam R. E. GOODIN, & C. TILLY, *Oxford Handbooks of Political Science*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [24]. Tsai, K. S. (2016). Adaptive Informal Institutions. Dalam O. Fioretos, T. G. Falleti, & A. Sheingate, *The Oxford Handbook of Historical Institutionalism*. Oxford : Oxford University Press.
- [25]. Wilson, I. D. (1999). Reog Ponorogo: Spirituality, Sexuality, and Power in a Javanese Performance Tradition. *Intersections: Gender and Sexuality in Asia and the Pacific*.
- [26]. Wilson, I. D. (2015). *The Politics of Protection Rackets in Post-New Order Indonesia*. London and New York: Routledge.